

Link of Blood in Urine with Exercise

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DOI: <http://doi.org/10.38177/AJBSR.2022.4304>

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Article Received: 13 May 2022

Article Accepted: 17 August 2022

Article Published: 23 September 2022

ABSTRACT

If someone is doing hard exercises after some pause, it is most probably, blood in urine. In this study was about linkage of blood in urine with exercise in which total 100 students participated studied in Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan. Hematuria is basically blood in urine and it causes some sever infection in urinary tract and also the test is performed to check the blood in urine.

Keywords: Hematuria, Bacterial or viral infection, Dipstick method.

1. Introduction

Blood in urine is termed as hematuria. It also has some urinary tract infections. And this infection is called as Cystitis. And some children including teens have red blood cells in urine. Some factors such as Age and infection due to bacteria or viral and strenuous exercise. Some people which are long distance runners really affected to the urinary bleeding. In this condition of hematuria kidney leak blood cells in urine or in any other ways.

Exercise provides the healthy fitness. Its moderate forms like fitness walking. Improve the efficiency of the body reduce the weight of body which indicate the reduction of certain severe diseases. If someone is doing hard exercises after some pause, it is most probably, blood in urine. The scientific worker has already been co-relate different parameter of a specific topic (1-4).

2. Materials and Methods

Dipstick test is performed to test the blood in urine, these are plastic strips. By dip the stick in the urine sample. Strips test used for the ingredient. Also these strips perform the test of white blood cells.

2.1. Study Organization

A Survey organized on the subject of the exercise.

2.2. Numerical Study

It were achieved by means of MS Excel

3. Results and Discussions

This project contained the link of blood in urine with exercise given in Table 1. In which the male or female participated and also collected the data from them. In which the presence or absence of blood in urine showed which further co relate with the exercise. About 67% people showed the likeness of blood in urine with exercise while 33% people not agreed with this. Which indicate the positive (presence) or negative (absence) of blood in urine.

Table 1. Link of Blood in Urine with Exercise

Blood in urine likeness	Blood in urine Dis-likeness
67%	33%

4. Conclusion

Questionnaire based studies have been given some research outcomes. The main causes of hematuria is the infection in the bladder and extreme exercise so that people have blood in urine. And sometimes it leads to the bladder or kidney cancer too.

Declarations

Source of Funding

This research did not receive any grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, and personal interests.

Ethical Approval

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan.

Consent for publication

Authors declare that they consented for the publication of this research work.

Availability of data and material

Authors are willing to share the data and material according to relevant needs.

Authors' Contributions

All authors equally contributed to data collection, research, and paper drafting.

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